

CURRENT STATUS OF SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT IN PARBHANI (MAHARASHTRA), INDIA

*Anil Khole

Department of Zoology, B. Raghunath College, Parbhani (M.S.) India.

*Corresponding Author: Anil Khole

Department of Zoology, B. Raghunath College, Parbhani (M.S.) India.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17482374>,

How to cite this Article: *Anil Khole. (2025). CURRENT STATUS OF SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT IN PARBHANI (MAHARASHTRA), INDIA. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Science, 11(11), 286–293.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 03/10/2025

Article Revised on 23/10/2025

Article Published on 01/11/2025

ABSTRACT

Parbhani City, located in Maharashtra, India, faces significant challenges in managing domestic sewage and solid waste. The absence of a comprehensive sewage treatment system has resulted in untreated effluents entering local water bodies, contributing to environmental degradation. Solid waste management has seen partial progress with the establishment of a biogas plant at Borwand, which processes wet waste into energy. However, low public compliance with waste segregation and limited infrastructure for dry waste and composting continue to hinder sustainable outcomes. This study examines the impact of solid waste and sewage dumping sites on public health, as well as air, soil, and water pollution in Parbhani. There is an urgent need to improve urban sanitation strategies to enhance public health and ecological resilience in the city.

KEYWORDS: *Parbhani city, Domestic sewage, Management, Public health, Sanitation.*

INTRODUCTION

Urbanization in Parbhani City, Maharashtra, has led to increased pressure on basic sanitation infrastructure, particularly in the management of domestic sewage and solid waste. The lack of adequate sewage treatment facilities results in untreated effluents entering natural water bodies, posing serious environmental and public health risks. Solid waste management has seen partial improvements through initiatives like the biogas plant at Borwand, yet challenges persist due to poor waste segregation and limited processing capacity. Domestic sewage is the leading cause of water pollution in India, with 78.7% of the 29,129 MLD generated remaining untreated; even after planned upgrades, 72.7% will still lack treatment (CPCB, 2021). This study examines the current status, infrastructural gaps, and emerging solutions in Parbhani's urban sanitation landscape, highlighting the need for integrated and sustainable waste management strategies.

Parbhani city, located in Maharashtra (M.S.), is a developing urban center with a growing population and expanding residential, commercial, and institutional activities. The domestic sewage and solid waste

generated here largely consists of wastewater from households, kitchens, toilets, and small establishments. However, the city lacks a fully efficient sewage collection and treatment infrastructure. Most of the sewage is directly discharged into open drains, low-lying areas, or nearby water bodies, leading to pollution of surface and groundwater sources. Therefore, it is essential to analyze the present status of domestic sewage and solid waste management in Parbhani city to identify the existing gaps, evaluate environmental and health impacts, and suggest sustainable solutions for the future.

METHODOLOGY

This study is based on observations from selected sites, data collection, information gathering, and a systematic literature review approach, focusing on existing studies, reports, and databases that explore public challenges. The literature review includes searches through bibliographic databases, peer-reviewed journals, reports, books, scientific reviews, SCOPUS, and open-access websites. This paper identifies both positive and negative impacts of solid waste generated across different sectors of the community.

Fig. 1. Map of Parbhani District

Urban Profile

Parbhani, located in the heart of Marathwada (M.S.) India, is known for its agricultural significance, historical temples, and evolving infrastructure. It's also a focal point for environmental planning, especially around water management and urban sanitation right.

Population

As of 2025, the estimated population of Parbhani city is approximately 447,000, based on projected growth trends since the last official census (www.census2011.co.in). This includes the urban agglomeration and reflects a steady annual increase of around 2% over recent years (worldpopulationreview.com).

Urban Local Bodies (ULBs)

Parbhani district comprises 9 municipalities and 1 municipal corporation, covering talukas like *Parbhani, Gangakhed, Sonpeth, Pathri, Manwath, Palam, Sailu, Jintur, and Purna.*

Major Rivers

Parbhani District is traversed by three major rivers Godavari (79 km), Purna (65–70 km), and Dudhana (81 km). The Godavari flows through key talukas like Pathri, Sonpeth, and Gangakhed, serving as a vital water source. Purna originates near Yeldari Dam and merges with the Godavari at Jambul bet, while Dudhana begins in Aurangabad hills and joins the Purna near Devthana.

Parameter	Status
Estimated Sewage Generation	~40–45 MLD (based on population & CPCB norms)
Installed Treatment Capacity	Very limited or absent in Parbhani city
Treatment Gap	Nearly 100% untreated discharge
Disposal Method	Mostly direct discharge into local drains and rivers

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Parbhani City, like many growing urban centers in Maharashtra, faces mounting challenges in managing domestic sewage and solid waste. The absence of a dedicated sewage treatment plant means that most wastewater is discharged untreated into local water bodies, contributing to environmental degradation and public health risks. This mirrors national trends, where over 70% of urban sewage remains untreated due to infrastructure gaps.

Solid waste management in Parbhani has seen partial progress. The biogas plant at Borwand, which processes approximately 10 tons of wet waste daily, represents a step toward sustainable waste-to-energy conversion. However, the effectiveness of this initiative is undermined by low public compliance with waste segregation norms. Mixed waste collection reduces the efficiency of composting and recycling efforts. Composting and dry waste processing units are under development, signalling institutional intent to improve waste handling. Yet, without robust public awareness campaigns, improved collection systems, and enforcement of segregation protocols, these facilities may fall short of their potential.

Current scenario of composition and solid waste management in India

According to TERI report (2023) waste management in India improved significantly after the 1994 Surat plague, prompting key policies and schemes for urban and rural sanitation. However, rising waste generation due to urbanization and population growth now challenges existing infrastructure.

India produces over 160,000 tons of municipal solid waste daily, driven by rapid urban growth, with 95.4% collected but only half scientifically treated leaving much of it in unregulated landfills that pose serious environmental and health risks (Anunay & Singh, 2022). India, with over 1.3 billion people, produces 62 million tonnes of solid waste annually, ranking as the world's third-largest generator (Sharma *et al.*, 2021). In India's waste generation is rising rapidly due to urban growth and shifting consumption habits, with 50–55% organic matter, 8–12% plastics, and the rest comprising paper, metals, and glass. In recent years, policymakers have prioritized waste management, introducing rules and policies to improve its implementation nationwide.

Current scenario of composition and solid waste management in Maharashtra State

In 2025, Maharashtra produces about 26,820 metric tons of daily municipal waste, mainly biodegradable organic matter (50–55%), followed by plastic (8–10%), paper/cardboard (6–8%), glass, metals, e-waste (3–5%), and construction debris (15–20%). These diverse wastes create challenges that drive innovations like decentralized composting, waste-to-energy, and smart monitoring across the state (MPCB, 2025). The efforts in Maharashtra's solid waste management are evolving, with Pune leading in door-to-door collection and segregation via SWaCH, while biomethanation, composting, and waste-to-energy projects in Mumbai and Nagpur drive sustainable disposal and recovery. The state produces 80 tons/day of biomedical waste from 75,000+ facilities, treated via autoclaving, incineration, and rural deep burial, with Mumbai and Pune expanding capacity post-COVID; hazardous waste exceeds 1.5 million tons annually, facing illegal dumping and limited CHWTSDF infrastructure. Under Environment Vision 2030, Maharashtra targets 100% scientific waste treatment, 60% MSW reduction by 2030, and integrates

climate resilience and resource conservation into its policy.

The current situation of solid waste & its Management in Parbhani city

In 2025, Parbhani city generates approximately 45–50 metric tons of municipal solid waste daily, mainly comprising biodegradable waste from food, gardens, and agriculture, along with plastic packaging and inert debris from minor construction activities. In Parbhani, waste is collected and transported to the *Dharroad* or *Borwand* dumping ground for storage, with door-to-door collection active in many wards, though source segregation remains inconsistent, and the city still lacks a scientific landfill or waste-to-energy facility. Joel *et al.*, (2025) The findings reveal that both landfills and open dumping sites pose significant threats to surface and groundwater resources, contributing to widespread contamination and ecological risk. In recent months, due to unresolved issues with municipal policy makers, door-to-door waste collection service (*ghanta gaddi*) providers in Parbhani have gone on strike, leading to disruptions in garbage management and increased dumping across the city. The current situation has some issues such as:

Fig. 2. Solid Waste Generation in Parbhani District (Source: DER, 2024)

1. Solid Waste Generation and Composition

While working on this issue, it was noted that Parbhani city generates around 45–50 metric tons of municipal solid waste daily, primarily composed of biodegradable waste suitable for composting and biogas, non-biodegradable plastic and packaging with low recycling rates, and inert construction debris from minor urban development. It was noted that, Parbhani city's solid waste is mainly composed of 40–60% biodegradable matter, 10–15% plastic, 5–10% construction debris, 5–8% paper and textiles, less than 2% rubber and leather, and under 1% hazardous materials. Sharma & Jain (2020) findings shown that developed countries follow the SWM hierarchy with a focus on reduce, reuse, and recycle, while low- and middle-income nations struggle with open dumping and weak waste infrastructure. Municipal solid waste (MSW) is typically categorized into food residues, wood, pulp, textiles, plastics, and rubber. Effective regulation enables recycling and reuse, benefiting society. Key treatment steps include on-site

handling, collection, transport, and final disposal (Johari *et al.*, 2014). A similar type of solid waste is recorded in Parbhani city, and when properly recycled and treated, it can offer significant benefits to society.

2. Collection of solid waste & its transportation issue

Large cities have efficient waste collection, but smaller towns and peri-urban areas face irregular pickup and poor disposal systems. Only 50–60% of urban homes get door-to-door waste collection, with minimal source segregation (Arvindan, 2021). Parbhani faces similar issues, including irregular waste collection and inadequate disposal systems. Research findings show that waste management practices fall into two categories: conventional methods such as collection, transport, and disposal, and innovative approaches that go beyond these basics. Parbhani faces irregular waste transport due to payment issues of the private agencies, causing prolonged service gaps and urban dumping problems. So efficient waste collection and transport are key to solid

waste management, typically handled by municipal bodies in urban areas. Limited financial resources, poor infrastructure, and rapid population growth impede full waste collection coverage.

3. *Overburdened landfills & dumping issue*

India's landfills are overburdened and poorly maintained, with major sites like Delhi, Ghazipur, Deonar, and Perungudi exceeding capacity. Unsegregated dumping causes fires, leachate contamination, and greenhouse gas emissions. The issue of Delhi's landfills has become increasingly political, especially with the approaching Assembly elections. Parbhani struggles with poorly maintained landfills and irregular waste transport, worsened by payment delays to waste transport contractors, leading to dumping and environmental risks at *Dharroad* and *Borwand* area. Toxic gases from landfills harm the environment and can cause lung and heart diseases, according to studies. Landfills produce toxic leachate through waste breakdown, leading to land and groundwater pollution (Swati *et al.*, 2018). The methane released from landfills has a great global warming potential which is 23 times greater than that of same amount of carbon dioxide (EIA 2003). In Parbhani, landfills are cost-effective but pose serious risks to health and the environment due to poor engineering.

4. *Use of Waste-to-Energy & Recycling Challenges*

Under Parbhani's solid waste management initiative, a biogas-based electricity generation unit has been commissioned to convert organic waste into biogas for energy production. Concurrently, proposed composting and dry waste processing facilities reflect a strategic transition toward integrated waste valuation at *Borwand* village. However, due to a technical problem, the unit is currently not operational. Savita *et al.*, (2025), emerging bio-electrochemical systems like microbial fuel cells (MFCs) use bacteria to produce electricity from organic waste, offering a low-emission energy solution still in early development. India produces 230 million metric tons of surplus agricultural waste, much of it burned or dumped due to infrastructure gaps and low awareness, causing significant pollution (The Hindu, 2025). The Ministry is promoting technologies to recover energy Biogas, Bio CNG, and Electricity from renewable agricultural, industrial, and urban wastes like municipal solid waste, market residues, and effluents (MNRE, 2025). Decentralized biogas units improve sanitation and energy access, SCADA systems enhance WtE efficiency, and MNRE offers up to ₹10 crore per project for Bio CNG and biogas power initiatives. Policymakers in Parbhani need to propose and advance initiatives for setting up Bio-CNG and biogas-based electricity generation projects. Treated residue or solid waste presents a valuable opportunity to boost clean energy production and generate additional income for Parbhani city.

Major Challenges in Solid Waste Management are

Solid waste management faces challenges such as poor infrastructure, low public awareness, and urban complexities that hinder efficient collection and disposal. Some key challenges are:

1. *Solid waste segregation & Public Awareness Issue*

Solid waste segregation and public awareness are major hurdles in urban sanitation for cities like Parbhani. Mixed waste disposal, poor infrastructure, and limited public engagement weaken recycling efforts. Changing perceptions, boosting education, and supporting informal workers are key to building a cleaner, more inclusive system. In Parbhani, solid waste segregation and public awareness remain key sanitation challenges. Despite planning efforts, mixed waste disposal persists due to low public engagement, poor infrastructure, and cultural attitudes. Informal workers play a crucial role but lack support. Strengthening education, school programs, and local awareness drives is vital for sustainable waste management. Source segregation is vital for solid waste management, especially with limited resources. Waste must be divided into wet, dry, and hazardous categories as per the 2016 rules. However, poor awareness and weak law enforcement hinder effective implementation (Pandey *et al.*, 2019). According to Charu & Vaishali (2025), proper waste segregation is essential to protect environmental and human health. In developing countries, unchecked dumping and rising consumer waste threaten safe disposal and increase health risks. Parbhani Municipal Corporation struggles with poor solid waste segregation and low public awareness. Despite planning efforts, mixed waste disposal persists due to weak outreach, cultural barriers, and inadequate infrastructure. Improving education, local engagement, and support for informal workers is key to better sanitation.

2. *Inadequate Collection and Transportation Infrastructure*

The solid waste management system in Parbhani city faces several infrastructural and operational challenges, particularly in the areas of collection and transportation. Parbhani city suffers from poor waste collection infrastructure limited door-to-door coverage (or collection only in particular areas), lack of source segregation, and inadequate public bins leading to frequent open dumping in streets and drains. The city is also suffering from the problems like traffic congestion, narrow roads, damaged roads and inefficient waste transportation schedules. In recent months, due to unresolved issues with municipal policy makers, door-to-door waste collection service (*ghanta gaddi*) providers in Parbhani city have gone on strike, leading to disruptions in garbage management and increased dumping across the city. This problem has been persisting for the past five to six years. The municipal corporation must find a permanent solution to it. Abhishek & Fozail (2024) noted that, the key challenges in India's C&D waste management low awareness, weak regulations, and poor

infrastructure resulting in unsustainable practices, unofficial dumping, and lack of recycling facilities. Solid waste management involves planning, funding, and operating systems for waste collection, transport, recycling, and disposal (Annepu, 2012). Parbhani Municipal Corporation must enhance waste collection, transportation systems, and staff training to address the city's inadequate solid waste infrastructure. In present Parbhani has 78 waste trolleys, 47 mini collection trucks, and 14 bulk transport trucks. While 43 composting units and 8 material recovery facilities exist, 2 bi-methanation units are urgently needed (DEP, 2020).

3. Overloaded Landfills and Open Dumping

India produces over 62 million tonnes of municipal solid waste annually, with nearly 70% mismanaged causing methane emissions, pollution, and biodiversity loss, while harming informal waste workers and hindering climate goals. Parbhani city is grappling with overloaded landfills and widespread open dumping, reflecting serious gaps in its solid waste management system. The existing landfill sites at Dharroad and Borwand are saturated, lacking essential features such as lining, leachate control, and gas management systems. The absence of scientific disposal has led to unmanaged waste accumulation and pollution due to the lack of engineered landfills. Shah & Pal (2024) noted that leachate from landfills contaminates groundwater and nearby surface water bodies, as observed in Ghazipur (Delhi) and Deonar (Mumbai). Landfills and open dumpsites are major sources of pollution and health

hazards, with marginalized communities bearing the greatest impact (Prashan, 2025). Parbhani city is also facing serious public health risks, including vector-borne diseases, groundwater contamination, and air pollution from burning waste.

4. Increasing Plastic and Biomedical Waste

Biomedical plastic waste is rising in India due to the widespread use of single-use medical items such as IV bags, syringes, gloves, and diagnostic packaging. Parbhani district generates 2.625 MTD of plastic waste, including 0.5 MTD from four ULBs. Seven ULBs ensure 100% door-to-door collection and segregation, supported by three Plastic Waste Collection Centres (DEP, 2020). This issue is also evident in Parbhani, which is facing increasing levels of plastic and biomedical waste—leading to environmental pollution, health hazards, and strain on its already inadequate waste infrastructure. According to Explore Medindia’s Hospital Directory, Parbhani district has 471 bedded hospitals (226 authorized), 185 non-bedded hospitals (88 authorized), 73 clinics, and seven veterinary hospitals, generating around 395 kg/day of biomedical waste (DEP Report, 2020). The widespread use of PPE such as masks, gloves, and medical plastics has further strained waste management systems in developing countries (Sahoo et al., 2023). Authorized plastic waste pickers operate in the district, which lacks both plastic manufacturers and recyclers (data to be verified); plastic waste is treated through road construction.

Fig. 3. Inventory of Biomedical Waste Generation

Figure 5 Details of Plastic Solid Waste Generation
Fig. 4. Estimated Quantity of Plastic Waste Generated in Dist.

E Waste Management

Millions of electronic devices are discarded as e-waste around the world each year, posing health and environmental risks if not properly recycled (WHO). E-waste includes items like computers, phones, appliances, and medical equipment. Improper recycling and disposal can release up to 1,000 harmful chemicals, including neurotoxins like lead (Balde *et al.*, 2024). A major e-

waste awareness and collection drive was conducted on January 26, 2025, in collaboration with Pune-based Purnam Eco-vision Foundation, establishing 13 collection centers across Parbhani for safe disposal. The district lacks an authorized e-waste recycler or dismantler but maintains linkage with external authorized facilities; however, poor management and disposal practices pose serious environmental hazards.

Fig. 5. Garbage accumulation near residential areas, Parbhani

Fig. 6. Garbage accumulation near Government Civil Hospital, Parbhani

Fig. 7. Garbage accumulation at vegetable market, Gandhi Park, Parbhani

Public Awareness and Community Participation

In India, solid waste management suffers due to inequality, poor awareness, limited information, health effects and mistrust in authorities. Rapidly growing regions face urgent solid waste challenges driven by rising population, industry, and consumption, demanding

effective management strategies (Zhang *et al.*, 2024). According to the World Bank, sustained solid waste management relies heavily on public awareness, trust, and participation across all stages from storage and segregation to recycling, payment, and facility

acceptance. The core components of public awareness are

- a) *Public awareness strategies (IEC Campaigns, Digital Outreach, Cultural Integration, Youth participation)*
- b) *Community Participation Models (Resident welfare association, Self-help groups, Ward committee)*
- c) *Behavioral & Institutional change (Source segregation, Incentives, Penalties, Monitoring tools)*

In Parbhani and Maharashtra, solid waste management is improving through Swachh Mission success stories, use

of local data, student-led campaigns, and traditional sanitation messaging. Currently, Parbhani’s urban growth is driving a surge in solid waste, straining infrastructure and causing health risks. Poor public awareness hampers segregation and community action. Therefore, community participation is key to sustainable solid waste management, with the 5 R’s Refuse, Reduce, Reuse, Repurpose, recycle empowering households to reduce environmental contamination.

No.	Precautions	Measures
1.	Source-Level Segregation	The district should adopt a 3-bin system and run awareness drives to boost waste segregation in homes and institutions.
2.	Strengthen Collection & Transport	Upgrade mini trucks and trolleys with GPS for efficient waste collection and route tracking.
3.	Infrastructure Enhancement	The district should add 2 bio-methanation units, expand composting beyond 43 sites, and boost material recovery centers above 8.
4.	Plastic & Biomedical Waste Control	Hospitals should enforce segregation, monitor PPE disposal, promote reusables, and link with certified recyclers.
5.	Community Engagement	Engage schools, colleges, and communities in clean-up drives, backed by rewards to promote waste reduction and recycling.
6.	Policy & Monitoring	Conduct ward-level audits and boost ULB compliance with DEP and CPCB norms for better waste management.

CONCLUSION

Parbhani city faces mounting challenges in domestic solid waste management due to rapid urbanization, limited infrastructure, and low public awareness. While initiatives like the Swachh Maharashtra Mission and student-led campaigns have sparked progress, sustainable improvement depends on stronger community participation, effective segregation, and integration of traditional practices with modern strategies. Continued efforts in education, data-driven planning, and inclusive governance are essential to build a cleaner, generating funds, healthier Parbhani. The solid waste management is not only vital for improving sanitation and public health in Parbhani but also essential for safeguarding the city’s environment and ensuring

sustainable urban development in the future. The tools mentioned in the District Environment Report must be followed by the public to maintain hygienic conditions in Parbhani.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I sincerely thank our Principal, Dr. V.Y. Sonawane, for his inspiring leadership and support. To the students, your dedication and teamwork across classrooms, labs, and fieldwork embody the spirit of our academic community.

REFERENCES

1. A. Singha, A. Kazmib, M. Starklc, S. Sayanekard, and M. Herlekar (2018). Sewage management

- challenges in mega cities in India: a case study of Mumbai, *Desalination and Water Treatment*, 116: 329–341.
2. Abhishek Singh & Fozail Misbah (2024). Identification and Analysis of Challenges Faced in the Collection, transportation and Disposal of c & d Waste Management in India, *IJARIE*, 10(2): 3817-3825.
 3. Aravindan M (2021). Solid Waste in India and its Management, *International Journal of Environmental Research*, 9(2): 145-160.
 4. Anunay A. Gour and S. K. Singh (2022). Solid Waste Management in India: A State-of-the-Art Review, *Environmental Engineering Research*.
 5. Annepu, R.K. (2012). Sustainable Solid Waste Management in India. Waste-to-Energy Research and Technology Council.
 6. Balde CP, Kuehr R, Yamamoto T, McDonald R, D'Angelo E, Althaf S et al. (2024). The Global E-waste Monitor 2024. Bonn, Geneva: International Telecommunication Union, United Nations Institute for Training and Resources; 2024 (<https://ewastemonitor.info/>).
 7. Charu Lata Singh & Vaishali Billa (2025). A Study On Issues And Challenges In Segregation And Disposal Of Household Solid Waste, *IJCRT*, 13(7): 931-941.
 8. District Environment Report (2020). Department Environment Plan & Pollution Department, Govt. of Maharashtra.
 9. Energy Information Administration (EIA) (2003) Emissions of Greenhouse Gases in the United States Comparison of global warming potentials from the IPCC's second and third assessment reports.
 10. Joel B. Njewa, Grace Mweta & Timothy Tiwonge Biswick (2025). The impact of dumping sites on air, soil and water pollution in selected Southern African countries: challenges and recommendations, *Water Emerg. Contam. Nanoplastics*, 4: 3. 10.20517/wecn.2024.71.
 11. Johari A, H. Alkali, H. Hashim, S. I. Ahmed, and R. Mat, "Municipal solid waste management and potential revenue from recycling in Malaysia, *Mod. Appl. Sci.*
 12. Kapil Dev Sharma & Siddharth Jain (2020). Municipal solid waste generation, composition, and management: the global scenario, *Social Responsibility Journal*, DOI: 10.1108/SRJ-06-2019-0210.
 13. Maharashtra Pollution Control Board (MPCB): Waste Management and; Circular Economy 2025, By cmaknowledge / August 28, 2025. <https://www.cmaknowledge.in>.
 14. Md Mainul Sk, Sajid Qamar & Trilochan Sethy (2023). Waste management in Indian perspectives: A comprehensive review, *Humanities & Social Sci. Studies*, 12(1): 35-45.
 15. Pandey A.K., Sahu R, & Tyagi R.V. (2019). Study on waste segregation at source is the key in municipal solid waste management in Delhi, *Indian J.Sci.Res.*, 18(2): 255-259.
 16. Prashant Ravish (2025). Sustainable Management of Landfill Sites in India: Addressing Environmental, Health, and Socioeconomic Challenges, *Curr World Environ*, 20(1): 104-111.
 17. Saha A, Pal SC, Islam ARMdT, Islam A, Alam E, Islam K. Hydrochemical based assessment of groundwater vulnerability in the Holocene multiaquifers of Ganges delta. *Scientific Reports*. 2024; 14(1).
 18. Supriya Prasad Patil (2025). A Comprehensive Review of Solid Waste Management in Indian Cities: Challenges, Policies, and Sustainable Solutions, *IJSRET*, 12(1): 227-235.
 19. Swati Wanwari, Indu Shekhar Thakur, Virendra Kumar Vijay & Pooja Ghosh (2018). Scenario of Landfilling in India: Problems, Challenges, and Recommendations, In book: *Handbook of Environmental Materials Management*, Publisher: Springer International Publishing AG, part of Springer Nature 2018.
 20. Sharma, H. B.; Vanapalli, K. R.; Samal, B.; Cheela, V. S.; Dubey, B. K.; Bhattacharya, J., (2021). Circular economy approach in solid waste management system to achieve UN-SDGs: Solutions for post-COVID recovery. *Science of The Total Environment*, 800: 149605.
 21. Savita Agarwal, Shraddha Kawale, Vidhi Singh, Piyush Mahajan & Reeta Pandey (2025). Advancements and Challenges in Waste-to-Energy Conversion Technologies: A Sustainable Approach to Waste Management, *IJETIR*, 5(3): 10-184.
 22. Sahoo S., Rathod W., Vardikar H., Biswal M., Mohanty S., & Nayak S.K. (2023). Biomedical waste plastic: bacteria, disinfection and recycling technologies—a comprehensive review, *Springer Nature*, 21: 1141-1158.
 23. Shweta Choudhary (2019). A Research Paper on Solid Waste Management, 2019 *JETIR*, 6(3): 561-567.
 24. TERI (2023). State of Waste Management Report New Delhi: The Energy and Resources Institute. 71pp. [Project Report No. 2021CW12].
 25. Zhang, Z., Chen, Z., Zhang, J., Liu, Y., Chen, L., Yang, M. et al., (2024). Municipal solid waste management challenges in developing regions: A comprehensive review and future perspectives for Asia and Africa. *Science of the Total Environment*, 172794. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.172794>.